

Blended Reading Instruction and a 3-Liner Story Comprehension Skills of Grade Two Learners

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effect of the blended reading instruction on the three-liner story for grade two learners. This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study would be the 85 grade two pupils – 43 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 42 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of role play has increased the historical appreciation skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. blended 2. reading instruction 3. 3-liner story comprehension

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1. Introduction

Many of the essential abilities a youngster may acquire are the ability to read and write. Most academic education is built based on the reading. Reading comprehension, speaking, and the count is essential for a child's academic and life success (Muijselaar et al., 2017). One of the Department of Education's top priorities is to enhance literacy (DepEd, 2020). It is based on the Department's flagship initiative, "Every Child A Reader Program," which tries to make each Filipino child a proficient reader and writer at their reading level. The Department of Education (DepEd) supports the Every Kid a Reader Program, which intends to make every Filipino child a reader and a writer at their grade level, as defined in the DepEd Order No. 14 series of 2020. Thus, due to the pandemic, the Department of Education will continue to deliver the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) evaluation to learners in public primary schools across the country through the Bureau of Learning Delivery-Teaching and Learning Division (BLDTLD). Grade Two teachers experience a transitory teaching-learning to read phase during this time of pandemic since engagement to a

print-rich environment with enjoyable surroundings with classmates playing words and singing nursery rhymes to build phonemic awareness are necessary where they understand the core skills involved in learning to read. The English and Filipino reading profile of learners, challenges, difficulties and lessons, the schools' agenda and initiatives for the enrichment of reading programs to eliminate these reading challenges and difficulties, and stakeholders' support and commitment. The suggested reading programs and activities may form part in the creation of contextualized reading curricula and be used as reading literacy initiatives in the schools. These initiatives are categorized as Literacy Program, Individual Reading Recovery Program and Enrichment/Enhancement Program. The quality of a person's life can be enhanced by the literacy level as the latter is directly related to his/her working life (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2008). There is a direct relationship between literacy and academic achievement. Hence, training individuals with good literacy who can comprehend and question what they read is one of the most important goals for today's education (Grove Hauptfleisch, 1982; Moreillan, 2007). Individuals who are regarded as smart as their peers but having poor reading abilities cannot improve it as much as their peers. As per record, all students pass elementary education. Corollary, even those who have poor reading ability pass their classes. They cannot perform reading at the level expected of their grade, resulting in anxiety and depression throughout their schooling. They are usually stereotyped as unsuccessful throughout their formal education. Such results in adoption problems in their classes (Bender, 2012). Reading is a complex process as it involves "sensation, perception, comprehension, application, and integration". It is the process of making and getting meaning from printed words and symbols. Reading is a means of communication and of information and ideas. Aracelo (1994) as cited by Panerio (2008) reported that "85Reading also plays a vital role in ones' success in school. It is one of the most important skills an individual learner must need to master. It is a prerequisite of all learning areas. It serves as a gateway for every learner to learn the different subjects because when a learner has a difficulty in reading, he/she may also encounter difficulties in all subject areas. Researches have shown that there are many reasons in the difference in the achievement level of the students. Luz (2007) stresses that many Filipino learners do not have the reading habit required in learning. As she noted, "The problem of non-reading lies at the heart of why the Philippines is so uncompetitive in the world economy and why so many of our people continue to live in poverty or barely escape it". The Philippines shared a significant rate of low performers among all PISA- participating countries and economies. That is, 80In response to this DepEd's 3Bs Initiatives, the Schools Division of Aurora has started its reading administration to elementary and junior high schools to assess the level of reading ability of the learners and determine their reading profile. It has a great hope that these learners who have reading difficulties can still be relieved of their reading problems by means of a suitable reading environment, teaching program and family support. The indispensable issue to be addressed here is the form the environment, program and support that should be undertaken. The reading environments must be designed to eliminate the reading difficulties of students to make them feel relaxed and willing to express themselves. In addition to this, students' learning must be supplemented with materials in consonance to their interests and abilities coupled with support from the teacher and students' family members. The research proves the "effectiveness of informing students about the difficulties they experience, and strategy-based programs conducted with the cooperation of the teacher and family" (Baydik,

O₁ x O₂

O₃ x O₄

Where:

O₁ - Pretest of the experimental group

O₂ - Posttest of the experimental group

O₃ - Pretest of the controlled group

O₄ - Posttest of the controlled group

--- - Non-random assignment of subjects

X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

2011; Torgesen, 2000; Westwood, 2008). The students' experienced difficulties in reading and learning could serve as a basis for a strategy-based program to be designed for them to have better reading skills. Hence, this study was conducted to assess the students' reading profile and perceived challenges in reading to serve as a basis for schools' agenda and initiatives for the enrichment of reading programs. In the Division of Davao Del Particularly in Maibo

Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, problem in reading comprehension particularly in the early grades is a prevailing issue especially that there is a learning gap caused by the pandemic. The researcher being a grade two teacher has come up with an intervention of implementing reading in a blended instruction so that even staying at home during pandemic the learners will still have reading activities. Hence, this study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact groups of learners. This design is represented as follows:

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 85 grade two pupils – 43 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 42 are

from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	43
2	Section B	42
	Total	85

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where the teacher gave printed modules and there were times of face to face and online sessions adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance test consists of a 25-item test will eventually determine the read-

ing skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the reading comprehension on the three-liner sentence of the grade two learners. On the hand, a posttest will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the comprehension level of the grade two learners on a three-liner sentence story, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts

of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Maibo Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the reading comprehension of grade two learners on a three-liner story

in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of the effect of blended reading approach on the reading skills of grade two learners in a three-liner story.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the

Scale Description for Student Performance

Interval	Scale	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced: The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing: The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning: The student at this level struggles with understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 14.3 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 14.6 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	43	14.3	57.2	Beginning
Experimental Group	42	14.6	58.4	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Devos, S.A., (2012 who said that such skills allow children to develop greater fluency, vocabulary, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, and writing skills. Unfortunately, many students lack fundamental reading skills, which results in poor performance on standardized tests, quizzes, and other assignments and negatively impacts future learning and opportunities (Devos, S.A., 2012). Reading also plays a vital role in ones' success in school. It is one of the most important skills

an individual learner must need to master. It is a prerequisite of all learning areas. It serves as a gateway for every learner to learn the different subjects because when a learner has a difficulty in reading, he/she may encounter also difficulties in all subject areas. Researches have shown that there are many reasons in the difference in the achievement level of the students. Luz (2007) stresses that many Filipino learners do not have the reading habit required in learning. As she noted, "The problem of non-reading lies at the heart of why the Philippines is so uncompetitive in the world economy and why so many of our people continue to live in poverty or barely escape it".

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	43	20.97	83.88	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group	42	21.15	84.60	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.97 or Approaching level while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.15 or Approaching level. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating in-

crease of 6.55 from a mean rating of 14.6 to 21.15. This means that the experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Adams (2000) who cited Students learn generic reading comprehension strategies such as finding the main idea, starting with simple paragraphs, and 5 moving to more complex material.

These strategies help build reading comprehension skills that will work with any reading material, not just particular stories or content children are reading. (Adams, 2000). One of the most important factors that impede a student's reading ability is phonemic awareness, which is the ability to process the individual sounds

of letters needed for word recognition. Poor working memory is another factor that affects a student's ability to read proficiently and understand text. Working memory allows a student to temporarily store information in short-term while engaging in cognitive tasks (Dawkins, L., 2017).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.40	.0322	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.40 with a p-value of .0322 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade two learners. This implies that the use of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills in teaching have contributed to the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the grade two learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Dawkins, L (2017) who said One of the most important factors that impede a students' reading ability is phonemic awareness, which is the ability to process the individual sounds of letters needed for word recognition. Poor work-

ing memory is another factor that affects a student's ability to read proficiently and understand text. Working memory allows a student to temporarily store information in short-term while engaging in cognitive tasks (Dawkins, L., 2017). Guided reading interventions offer a unique experience for readers. It promotes opportunities for the development of a self-extending system. It allows readers to read with students who have similar abilities, and it can make them feel comfortable with their abilities if they are striving towards success. If students exceed reading expectations, guided reading is where they can continue to scaffold their knowledge. Students dialogue regarding the familiar text in the group will further develop their understanding because they can learn from each other (McCullum, A., 2016)

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 6 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
85	-4.22	0.325	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills approach on the reading skills of grade two learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.325 which signifies a large effect. This implies that

teachers should look for a strategy in teaching reading and that teachers have a pivotal role in helping children to develop and maintain a positive attitude towards learning and literacy. Motivated readers read more, use more com-

plex cognitive strategies, and thus become better readers. To motivate children to read, classroom teachers: demonstrate a passion for reading; act as model readers for their students; know how children perceive the value of reading, and aim to enhance the perceived value by linking reading with the children's own interests and goals. Reading Interventions allow students to

read more while in school. Reading interventions, including guided reading with teachers, provide instructional support, daily experience with fluency, comprehension, vocabulary, phonics, phonemes, and exposure to a wide variety of genres and types of texts to become more proficient readers (Richardson, J., 2009).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills approach on the reading appreciation skills of grade two learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 85 grade two pupils – 43 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 42 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of role play has increased the historical appreciation skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores both the experimental and control groups' post-test results are at the approaching level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching reading both English and Filipino should use blended reading instruction since blended reading instruction combines the benefits of direct teacher-student interaction with the flexibility of online learning resources. Traditional reading instruction often involves guided reading sessions, discussions, and assessments conducted in a classroom setting. In contrast, digital tools offer interactive e-books, online quizzes, and multimedia resources that cater to diverse learning styles and paces. By merging these approaches, educators can provide a more personalized learning experience that can adapt to the individual needs of students. The school heads should promote the use of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study that this method also allows for

differentiated instruction, where students can work on tasks suited to their specific reading levels and abilities. For example, struggling readers can access additional support and practice through online tutorials, while advanced readers can explore more challenging materials. Furthermore, digital platforms can track student progress in real-time, offering immediate feedback and allowing teachers to adjust their instructional strategies accordingly. A school policy about the utilization of role play can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of blended reading instruction and 3-liner story comprehension skills as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Adams, M. J. (2000). Advancing our students' language and literacy: The challenge of complex texts. *American Educator*, 34(4), 3.
- Al Saud, A. F. (2021). The effect of blended learning on children's arabic reading during covid-19 quarantine. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 14(12), 1132–1152.
- Alammary, A., Sheard, J., & Carbone, A. (2014). Blended learning in higher education: Three different design approaches. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 30(4), 440–454. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.693>
- Alvarez Jr, A. V. (2020). Learning from the problems and challenges in blended learning: Basis for faculty development and program enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112–132.
- Baydik, B. (2011). Investigation of students with reading difficulties' use of metacognitive reading strategies and their teachers' reading comprehension teaching practices. *Education and in Science* 36, 162, 301–319.
- Bender, W. N. (2012). *Project-based learning: Differentiating instruction for the 21st century*. Corwin Press.
- Brandt, L., Gardner, K., & Clark, S. K. (2020). Providing proximal rewards: Rethinking reading rewards and motivation. *The Reading Teacher*, 77(6), 927–936.
- Dawkins, L. D. (2017). *Factors influencing student achievement in reading* [Doctoral dissertation, Walden University].
- Devos, S. A. (2012). Reading for the technical workplace: Developing a diagnostic reading assessment for understanding instructional texts. *TESL Canada Journal*, 40(2), 41–61.
- Fasko, S. N., & Fasko Jr, D. (2010). A preliminary study on sight word flash card drill: Does it impact reading fluency? *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, 61, 69.
- McCullum, A. (2016). *The relationship between fluency and comprehension in second grade students* [Doctoral dissertation, Goucher College].
- Muijselaar, M. M., Swart, N. M., Steenbeek-Planting, E. G., Droop, M., Verhoeven, L., & de Jong, P. F. (2017). Developmental relations between reading comprehension and reading strategies. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 21(3), 194–209.

- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2022). Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- O'Rourke, E. (2017). *The impact of effective guided reading practices* [Doctoral dissertation].
- Panerio, R. O. (2008). *Reading comprehension skills of gubat south central school* [Master's thesis, Bicol University Campus].
- Richardson, A. J., Burton, J. R., Sewell, R. P., Spreckelsen, T. F., & Montgomery, P. (2009). Docosahexaenoic acid for reading, cognition and behavior in children aged 7–9 years: A randomized, controlled trial (the dolab study).
- Torgesen, J. K. (2000). Individual differences in response to early interventions in reading: The lingering problem of treatment resisters. *Learning disabilities research practice, 15*(1), 55–64.
- Westwood, P. (2008). *A parent's guide to learning difficulties: How to help your child*. Aust Council for Ed Research.